

Original Article

District Ramban and Agricultural Practices -A Review

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Increase in agricultural production and rise in per capita income of the country especially rural community together with the Urbanization, leads to increase in demand in industrial production. It seems that increased agricultural output and productivity tends to contribute substantially to an overall economic development of the country. It will be rational and appropriate to place greater emphasis on further development of agriculture sector.

Keywords: Urbanization, productivity, Rational Prosperity, Contribution.

Introduction:

Agriculture is the most important sector of the Indian economy. It is the major source of livelihood for the people and important source of income for the economic growth. Agriculture plays a very important role in Indian economic development. Besides, it is a way of life therefore general well being of the people lies its development. The state of Jammu and Kashmir is the big source of economic development of the country as well as for state of Jammu and Kashmir. The people of Jammu and Kashmir are associated directly or indirectly with agricultural activities they are engaged in agricultural practices in one way or other as they produced different crops and vegetables in different parts of the state of Jammu and Kashmir. District Ramban is also a part of Jammu and Kashmir state and is a hub of agriculture activities different agriculture activities are carried out by different people in different parts of the district. District Ramban is situated on the foot hills on the bank of river Chenab in Jammu Province. The district is all mountainous and has a tough terrain. River Chenab passes through the lower part of the district in between steep mountain ranges and is area of high economic importance. The total geographical area of the district is 1527.05 Km. It comprises of eleven blocks covering 129 Panchayats 132 villages.

Ramban district has shown an exponential growth in agriculture sector various crop & vegetables are produced & cultivated different part of the district Ramban several areas have fertile land where different crop are being produced these areas are Neel in Tehsil Ramsoo, Pogal Paristan, Gool Sangaldan in Ramban, and Mahoo Manjit Akhran Kawna etc. these areas are very rich in producing walnut, Apricot, Apple, maize and Wheat. Neel Pogal Paristan Senabathi Dardahi Chacka Sarbhagni in Ramsoo Tehsil. Khari Mahoo Manjit in Khari Tehsil. These are the places where crop like rice, wheat & Maize are produced in a large-scale. Majority of production in these areas are maize. These places have a lot of potential of producing different crops, but unfortunately the department has not adopted their areas under (CIVDP) Chenab intensive vegetable development project. Under the (CIVDP) programmers the agriculture department has adopted Five villages viz kenth, pernote in tehsil Ramban Asher and Mahu in tehsil Khari and chhachhawa in tehsil Gool the project formers are provided logistical technical and material assistance to increase farm income and adopt organic farming. According to chief Agriculture officer (CAO) the agriculture departmental has adopted 20 hectare land of 50 progressive farmers in each adopted village to achieve the Prime Minister Narendra Modi's aim of doubling their income in future.

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Encouraged by the assistance of the agriculture department the farmers of these villages believe that very soon they would double their income. A farmer, Badrinath claimed that this year pea worth Rs 40 lakh was sold in the market from Kanthi village alone. As per the official figures last year these five villages produced 4500 Qtl vegetable having market value of 11.25 Crore. Despite Prevailing COVID-19 situation, the farmers in coordination with agriculture department are determined to surpass the last year target. The farmers are looking forward for hefty returns through organic farming and off season crop production with the help of subsidized hybrid seeds, implements, water pipes, vermicompost units etc.

During the COVID-19 lockdown the department has provided 680 Qtl of high quality of Pulses, Fodder and Maize seeds costing Rs, 63.69 lacks to farmers on subsidized rates, besides providing 6419 Qtl fertilizers through registered dealers across the district. The collection and trade of (Anardana dehydrated wild pomegranate arils) serve as important livelihood option for rural communities around district head Qatar Ramban Kabi Gandri pernotekanga Marog etc. contribution up to 57.19% of total household income in some villages. Another farming activity beekeeping under Apiculture sector is growing by leaps and bounds in district Ramban especially in sub division Ramsoo and Banihal about 430 families are involved in this farming. As per the chief Agriculture officer Ramban (CAO) 2360 Qntl honey having market value Rs 11 crore was produced during the year.

Literature Review:

Agriculture plays a vital role in the economy of Ramban district in Jammu and Kashmir. Front line demonstration (FLDs) on maizecultivation have shown significant improvement in yield and profitability, with deno plots yielding 43.75% higher than local varieties and providing a better benefit -cost ratio. (Gupta2024.)

The collection of and trade of Anardana serve for the upper reaches of people of Ramban dehydrated wild pomegranate arils give benefit to rural communities in the region. Contribution up to 57.19% of total household income in some villages. (Mushtaq and Ganga -2017)

The district Ramban of Jammu and Kashmir cover an area of 113787 hectare and falls in the temperature zone of the state. it is an upland valley in the north east corner of Jammu division. Soil sample were collected from the entire Ramban district in a stratified random manner. (Indian journal of Ecology) The district Ramban of Jammu and Kashmir document present status and socio-economic profile of the families involved in the collection and trade of Anardana (Punica granalam; Dhru towards better livelihood options for the rural communities.

The random survey of Ganote, Dharam, Gool, Farmoot, Sangaldan, Gundi, Maha Kind and Chanderkote Revealed each household in these areas collects 400-500 kgs of dried seed, with per household annual collection touching 550-625 kgs in Kanga and pernote villages of Ramban. The study also revealed also that the annual income from Anardana was highest in Kanga village (Rs 285991/ ha with 57.19% contribution to total household income, while it was lowest in Ganote (Rs 176500/ha (41.11%) Study carried out by (Shahnawaz Mushtaq 2017)

The unique climatic Conditions of the region influence cropping patterns of productivity. These studies highlight the potential for improving agricultural practices and diversifying income sources to enhance rural livelihood in Ramban and the broader Kashmir valley. (Hussain – 2020)

Research Methodology:

For analyzing and assessing the agricultural practices of district Ramban, both primary source of data, and secondary source of data have been used. The primary source of data collected through intensive field work in different parts of District Ramban. Group discussions and non-participatory observations. For secondary source of data research opted for different Journals.

Conclusion:

The district Ramban have a great potential in the field of agriculture and people living in the district are engaged passionately in different agricultural activities. Due to the continuous efforts of the agriculture department and government interference in agricultural production district Ramban is growing in right way in this field. Lot of efforts and focus of government on this particular district is the need of time all the government schemes must be implemented and farmers should be encouraged through the agricultural schemes govt must focus on rural areas where production ratio is good and people have interest in agricultural production.

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